

Preservation of Antiquities from Media (1962–1974)

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Abstract

Journals magazines and newspapers were the most important media between 1962 and 1974. Media can give us about political, economic and social condition the time under survey. For social point of view the preservation of Cultural Heritage is also important for the country. For Preservation of Revolutionary Council government passed Antiquities Preservation Act of 1962. By this law, rules and regulations on preservation of antiquities, prohibition of ancient artefacts to abroad, forbidding and controlling the excavation of ancient sites, specifying of ancient building which were preserved by the government and punishments were defined. Moreover, the Revolutionary Council Government had done the measures for the excavation of ancient sites, renovation of ancient buildings, recording researching and maintaining of ancient inscriptions, deciphering, recording and researching ink painting and mural painting in historical sites. In the period under surveying, the State and Archaeological Department made great efforts to get antiquities from abroad. This paper analyzes the facts on the activities of the State about the preservation of cultural heritage from 1962 to 1974 with special references to media in Myanmar.

Keywords: preservation, culture, revolutionary council, antiquities

Introduction

Myanmar has been governed by a military dictatorship since the 1960s, but during the past twenty years or so, it has, achieved certain results in the field of conservation and restoration of various aspects of cultural heritage. Cultural heritage surveys, studies and conservation activities in Myanmar began during the British colonial period under the initiative of the Archaeological Survey of India. Laws that are currently in effect for cultural heritage protection in Myanmar include the Antiquities Act, which was enacted in 1957 and revised in 1962, and the Protection and Preservation of Cultural Heritage Regions Law, which was enacted in 1988, revised in 2009 and supplement in 2011 with regulations. The government also tried to maintain the traditional arts and culture. Media is the fourth Estate of the country and it also means as a mass communication and it includes journals, magazines and newspapers. Media can give us political, economic and social conditions of the time under survey and it can also provide the historical facts. By using the media's sources and materials, we explore and express the cultural history of Myanmar during the year from 1962 to 1974. So, the purpose of this paper is to examine the impact of media about the preservation of cultural heritage.

Preservation of Antiquities from Media (1962-1974)

Antiquities are historical evidences. Each of the antiquity tells the history of its period. However, some people lack the knowledge of historical value so they had destroyed ancient antiquities. For the preservation of cultural heritage, the government also passed Antiquities Preservation Act of 1962. Under this law, punishments were defined for the smuggling of antiquities abroad and for renovation ancient buildings which did not get the order to renovate from the government.¹ By this law, the following antiquities for historical evidences are:

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¹ [**၂၀၀၇**] (Hanthawady Newspaper), 25 December 1971

- a) human bones fossil
- b) ancient caves, sites, debris and remains and marks on religion,
- c) natural caves or dwelling places,
- d) ancient buildings, mounds which were used as roads and bridges at present, pagodas, cemetery and burial grounds, wells, natural lakes, ponds, earth bankers, façade of gateways, remains of moats or fortress
- e) utilities and artefacts which were believed to be used by ancient men or animals
- f) bold reliefs, painting, figures, pictograph and inscriptions which recorded on historical accounts and differentiation of races
- g) mould reliefs, coins, epigraphic scripts, handwriting, printed matter or things which were made of metal, stone, clay, wood, cloths, leather etc. which depicted about the settlement in ancient time.

By this law, rules and regulations on preservation of antiquities, prohibition of ancient artefacts to abroad, forbidding and controlling the excavation of ancient sites, specifying of ancient building which were preserved by the government and punishments were defined.

The following antiquities had been forbidden to smuggle abroad. These are:

- a) ancient stone tools
- b) stone fossils
- c) ancient Myanmar coins and symbols (Sriksetra, Hanlin, Rakhine, Hanthawady and Konbaung)
- d) things which lasted for more than seventy-five years
 - i. Myanmar weights

Buddha statues smuggled from Kyaington

Buddha statues in votive tablet

Sources: U Win, [\[a&sa \[mi typntumug f&etofa&\]\]](#) (“Preservation and Prohibition of Ancient”), Forward Journal, Vol. 23, No. 2, 15 June 1971, pp. 12-13 (Hereafter cited as “Preservation and Prohibition of Ancient”)

**Ancient bangle with a dragon image excavated from Ou Hnaungkon village,
Myinmu Township**

Earthen tobacco pipes

Sources: “Preservation and Prohibition of Ancient”

If any person smuggled these things to abroad shall be punishable with imprisonment for a term which may extend from six months to three years, with fine which may extend from 500 kyats to 5,000 kyats.² In preservation of cultural heritage, an archaeological activity is very important. Therefore the Revolutionary Council Government had done the measures for the excavation of ancient sites, renovation of ancient buildings, recording, researching and maintaining of ancient inscriptions, deciphering, recording and mural painting in historical sites. The government had developed to preserve national cultural heritage. Thus the historical links could be connected by archaeological activities.³ Antiquities are cultural heritage of nation. Safeguarding antiquities is not only for preservation of the nation’s culture but also for the maintenance of historical account of the country. During that period, Archaeological Department had excavated ancient Pyu sites, such as Baikthano, Hanlin and Sriksetra.

Systematic excavations at Hanlin from 1962 to 1967 have shed further light on the cultural complex of the ancient site. Earthen funerary urns were found. Moreover, in 1964, a huge inscribed stone slab was discovered about two furlongs north of the palace site. In 1967, Archaeology Department had excavated Pyu’s site in Sriksetra, Hmawza. Coins, golden bell, silver bell, gold plate, gold string and other jewellery which were used in Pyu Period had been excavated. Moreover brass statues were found on this site. These antiquities brought to shed light the standard of Pyu civilization.⁴

In December 1970, 1,200 silver coins were excavated at eastern and northern villages of Myohaung, Rakhine.⁵ In 1971, 350 Pyu Coins were found in Kyaikkatha village, Kyaikhto Township. Moreover, forty-five coins were excavated in Ayadaw Township, Monywa District.

² [http://www.burmesecalendar.com](#) (The Mirror), 15 June 1973

³ [http://www.burmesecalendar.com](#) (The Working People’s Daily), 21 August 1971

⁴ [http://www.burmesecalendar.com](#) (Hanthawady Newspaper), 21 August 1971

⁵ [http://www.burmesecalendar.com](#) (The Working People’s Daily), 26 October 1972

These coins were probably about 2000 years ago.⁶ On 18 March 1973 a stone slab which bears the nativity of the Buddha was excavated in Bagan by Archaeological Department. Moreover, Rakhine coins had been found in Yathetaung, Rakhine State on 25 September 1974. These coins have nine different sizes. On 30 September 197 a sand stone slab of Amarapura period was brought to light under Dhammayone- community hall for religious purpose, Pathiisu Quarter in Amarapura. In 1971, ancient monastery which decorated and adorned with various figures had yielded in Pakokku.⁷

With the encouragement of Archaeological Department and the State, Myanmar people donate antiquities which were kept in their own hand to Archaeological Department. On 25 January 1973 U Kyauk and Saw Seinn Yin donated Royal regalia which were worn by MahaMinhtin Sithu U Saw and his wife, KhinPhwagyi. U Saw was an officer of the court who received and transmitted the king's orders in the reign of King Mindon. Ancient coins and currency was donated to National Museum on 24 November 1971. These currencies were made of silver, alloy and bronze and had used in Myanmar and Thailand during the period from 1883 to 1945.⁸ On 2 June 1973 U Ye Hla donated four golden Brahminical duck which were excavated at ShweTaungto National Museum. Moreover, most of the people gave historical photos such as photos of Generals and battles to official concerns. Thus, these things gave the next generation to love the nation and develop the patriotism.

In that period, the State and Archaeological Department made great efforts to get antiquities from abroad. Therefore the British Government gave back royal insignias to Myanmar Government on 11 November 1964. These royal insignias were taken over by the British in 1886 when the British occupied Myanmar. And then the British preserved them in Victoria and Albert Museum, London from 1890. Toward the amicable relations between the two countries, the British gave back 164 royal insignias to Myanmar.⁹ They are exhibited in National Museum at present. For the preservation of cultural heritage, the moats and walls of Ratanapon Palace were renovated as former condition and golden monastery in Mandalay was restored. Mural paintings from Bagan, Nyang U, Monywa, Pakokku, Sagaing, Myin Mu and etc. were preserved with scientific methods.¹⁰

⁶allU;rlbwifpm (The Mirror), 3 January 1971

⁷[lbm0wlbwifpm (Hanthawady Newspaper), 25 December 1971

⁸wplvtwifpmayEsh, Obusrbwif (The Monthly New of Literature and Culture), NgweTayi Magazine, No. 139, January 1972, P. 156

⁹jynwifaf&m ("Domestic Affairs"), Forward Journal, Vol. 6, No. 1, 1 December 1964, P.3

¹⁰Min Naing, , Obusrri0Epf& (10 Years Journey of Culture), NgweTayi Magazine, Vol. 22, No. 3, 1970

Mr. Patrick Goldwin Walker, the British Foreign Minister handed over an item of Myanmar regalia to General Ne Win

Royal sash

Sources: (Domestic Affairs’), Forward Journal, Vol.6, No. 1, 1 December 1964, p.3 (Hereafter cited as “Domestic Affairs”)

Left lion beaker, Right spittoon and Left beaker

Rice bowl and Bigbetal box

Sources: "Domestic Affairs", p.4

Hamsā Goglet

Royal pedals

Sources: "Domestic Affairs", p.4

The Royal dagger of Alaungmintaya

Sources: "Domestic Affairs", p.4

Thus with the collaboration of the State, Ministry of Culture, Archaeological Department and the people, ancient monuments and antiquities had been preserved to a certain extent. The number of ancient monuments had increased from 120 in 1962 to 540 in 1974.¹¹ Archaeological Department spent about 700,000 kyats annually for the preservation of ancient monuments.¹²

Conclusion

Since humans have been existed on earth, they have built their own cultures based on their background and environment. These cultural heritages transmitted from generation to generation, are constantly recreated by communities and groups, in response to their environment, their interaction with nature and their history, thereby provide them with a sense of identity and continuity which can promote respect for cultural diversity and human creativity. Thus it is imperative to safeguard such these long-standing traditions and cultural heritages for the next generation. The governments concerned have formed many committees with the participation of experts in order to take the suggestion from relevant bodies aiming to protect and preserve ancient artefacts and edifices. From 1962 to 1974, the Revolutionary Council Government had done the preservation of ancient monuments and antiquities. The Government enacted the law to prohibit strictly smuggling to abroad. Under the supervision of Ministry of Culture, the Archaeology Department had excavated many ancient sites such as Hanlin and Sriksetra. These excavations could be proved that Myanmar people lived high standard of civilization since ancient time. It seems that the State and the people endeavored to safeguard antiquities as much as they could.

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¹¹ Paw Tun]]pmtlyavmu}} ("The World of Book"), NgweTayi Magazine, No. 169, July 1974, p.120

¹²]]wplvwlf pmayEst h Obausrbwif}} ("The Monthly New of Literature and Culture"), Ngwetayi Magazine, No. 151, January, 1973, p. 161

အိမ်ထောင်ရေး (NgweTayi Magazine), No. 139, January, 1972.

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